

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF *DURANTA REPENS* LINN

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Two crystalline compounds, identified as β -sitosterol and ursolic acid, have been isolated from the fruits of *Duranta repens* Linn.

Duranta repens Linn (syn. *Duranta plumieri* Jacq.) (Family Verbenaceae) is an erect shrub found throughout India and is cultivated in gardens as a hedge plant. The fruits are nonedible and are reported to contain an alkaloid (Bootsma, *Meded. Lands Plantentuin*, Java, 1899, 31, 122) and a fatty oil (Kafuku and Hata, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1936, 57, 727). The juice of the macerated fruits has also been found to be an effective larvicide (Manson, *J. Malar. Inst., India*, 1939, 2, 85).

In view of the reported insecticidal properties of this plant (Chopra, Badhwar and Ghosh, "Poisonous Plants of India", 1949, p. 57) it was considered desirable to undertake a detailed study of the fruits. The air-dried, powdered fruits on extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) yielded a mixture of a substance (A) and a waxy material. This was hydrolysed with ethanolic KOH (10%) and the unsaponified material was chromatographed over alumina using petroleum ether and benzene-chloroform as successive eluents. The benzene-chloroform fractions on concentration and crystallisation from methanol afforded a pure substance (A), m.p. 136°, identified as β -sitosterol.

The defatted powdered fruit was then extracted with ethyl acetate, which on concentration yielded a pale yellow amorphous powder. This on purification and repeated crystallisation from ethanol and acetone gave the substance (B), m.p. 278°. Comparison of (B) and its various derivatives with those of ursolic acid indicates its identity with that of the latter (Table I). Final confirmation was achieved by undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

TABLE I

Compound.	Formula.	Ursolic acid†.		Ursolic acid from <i>Duranta repens</i> Linn.	
		M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$ (CHCl ₃).	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$ (CHCl ₃).
Ursolic acid	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₉	286-87°	+70	278°	+70°.1
Acetylursolic acid	C ₃₂ H ₅₀ O ₄	286-87°		279°	
Methyl ursolate	C ₃₂ H ₅₀ O ₃	171°	+69°	168°	+68°.0
Acetylmethyl ursolate	C ₃₄ H ₅₂ O ₄	246-47°		243°	

† Simonsen and Ross, "The Terpenes", 1957, vol. V, p. 114.

EXPERIMENTAL

The powdered, air-dried fruits (5 kg.) were extracted first with hot petroleum ether and then with ethyl acetate.

Petroleum Ether Extract

The pale yellow petroleum ether extract was concentrated (weighed 100 g.) and then hydrolysed by refluxing on a water bath for 12 hours with EtOH-KOH (10%). The excess of ethanol

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was removed under vacuum, diluted with water and repeatedly extracted with petroleum ether. The residue left after removal of the solvent (weighed 30 g.) was dissolved in minimum amount of petroleum ether and chromatographed over alumina (900 g.), using petroleum ether and benzene-chloroform (3 : 2) as successive eluents. The forerun with petroleum ether was waxy in nature; from the benzene-chloroform fractions β -sitosterol was isolated, which crystallised from methanol in colorless plates (5 g.), m.p. 136°, $[\alpha]_D - 34^\circ.5$ (chloroform). It develops a pink coloration changing to blue and then green in the Liebermann-Burchard reaction and shows no depression in m.p. on admixture with an authentic sample. (Found : C, 84.14; H, 11.98. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{50}O$: C, 84.05; H, 12.07%).

β -Sitosterol Acetate.— β -Sitosterol (0.5 g.) on heating with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.) for 2 hours furnished the acetate (0.42 g.). It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 126°, $[\alpha]_D - 41^\circ.3$ (chloroform). (Found : C, 81.32; H, 11.78. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.57; H, 11.40%).

Ethyl Acetate Extract

This extract on concentration afforded a yellow amorphous residue (37.5 g.), which on decolorisation with charcoal and several crystallisations from ethanol and acetone furnished ursolic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 278°, $[\alpha]_D + 70^\circ.1$ (chloroform). It develops a violet coloration, which immediately changes to blue and finally turns green in the Liebermann-Burchard reaction. Mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample showed no depression. (Found : C, 78.58; H, 10.82. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$: C, 78.72; H, 10.52%).

Acetylursolic acid was prepared by heating ursolic acid with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 279°, $[\alpha]_D + 68^\circ.0$ (chloroform). (Found : C, 76.72; H, 10.34. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{50}O_4$: C, 77.10; H, 10.04%).

Methyl ursolate was prepared by treating ursolic acid with an ethereal solution of diazomethane. It was crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 168°. (Found : C, 78.74; H, 10.28. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.14; H, 10.63%).

Acetylmethyl ursolate was prepared by heating methyl ursolate with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. It was crystallised from acetone in colorless needles, m.p. 243°. (Found : C, 77.03; H, 10.43. Calc. for $C_{33}H_{52}O_4$: C, 77.32; H, 10.15%).

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